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Predicting trends in research using research community imports and exports

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Abstract: A novel method for tracking (and possibly predicting) trends in research is presented. In addition to tracking what a research community produces, we illustrate how to track the ‘import’ and ‘export’ of ‘micro-solutions’ to and from research communities over time. To illustrate this method, we graph production, import and export activities for the three research communities most associated with the literature on ‘emerging research topics’ over a 20-year period. Predicted levels of import, production and export activity are provided.

Introduction

For over 30 years, the authors of this paper have been involved in a research community that has focused on a very difficult problem – the characterization of the structure and evolution of research using bibliometric techniques. This problem has been referred to as ‘science mapping’ because of the map-like visualizations that have been used to portray the structure of scientific fields and topics using bibliographic data. Given the actual intent of these activities, a more precise phrase might be ‘mapping the structure and evolution of the indexed research literature’.

This work is intended to contribute to our research community by introducing a novel method for identifying and tracking the import and export activities of the tens of thousands of research communities that represent world-wide research. A case example illustrates how this new method can be operationalized.

The article is structured in the following fashion. Section 1 focuses on the theoretical underpinnings of this work. Section 2 describes the methodology employed. Section 3 presents and discusses the trend data for our case example. Section 4 provides some discussion and we close with implications of this work for forecasting research trends.

Section 1: Theoretical Framework

According to a recent analysis of 1600 documents related to emerging research topics (Xu, Hao, An, Pang, & Li, 2020), the dominant theoretical framework of this research area comes from Derek de Solla Price. Price characterized his perspective in terms of an emphasis on the

role of measurement (vs. theory) as the “force that moves science forward”.¹ Articles represent a packet of knowledge.² Price (1965) also argued that one should focus attention on the research front – the most recent articles that represent the “epidermal layer” of research.

The theoretical framework for our work over the years is not, however, based on Price. We draw from Thomas Kuhn’s (1970) concept of a research community. He argued that the underlying social structure of research is a community of researchers who are organized around a very difficult problem over a relatively long time. The average size of a research community was posited at about 100 people. There may be a diverse group of actors with different expectations in a research community. The actors may, in fact, be competing labs. But despite this diversity, there is a general consensus among the actors that there is a problem that is difficult to solve and worth working on in a collective fashion.

We have built on Kuhn to predict whether a research community will undergo exceptional growth (Klavans, Boyack, & Murdick, 2020). And what we have found is that history matters, far more than we expected. The best predictor is not what is happening at the research front but rather is based on a 10-year history of publication activity by that research community.

In this paper, we extend the scope of that work to include predicting links between research communities. We suggest that articles, while they can be viewed as a contribution to knowledge, can also be viewed as micro-solutions associated with the micro-problem that the authors have selected. The article is then cited by members of that community if it contributes to solving one aspect of the broader problem that the community is working on. The article might be cited by members of other research communities if it helps to solve an aspect of their problem. These are cases of an import of a micro-solution by the citing community and export of a micro-solution by the cited community. The following section describes how one might measure this phenomenon and forecast trends in production, import and export activity.

Section 2: Methodology

The 49.3 million indexed documents in the Scopus database (through 2020) have been organized into 98,742 Kuhnian research communities using the method of Boyack & Klavans (2022). The production of papers by a research community is a simple count of the number of papers over time that are assigned to that research community.

Yearly import and export activities are based on those documents where an article is assigned to one research community and has at least 4 references to another research community. Assume, for example, that a document is assigned to community A but has 4 references that are assigned to community B. One can interpret this pattern as an example of community A ‘importing’ a micro-solution from community B (and correspondingly community B is ‘exporting’ a micro-solution to community A). These instances of import and export activity are summed for each pair of research communities by year.

The three research communities that we use to represent the area of emerging research topics are associated with the roughly 1600 documents that were identified by Xu et al. (2020). We were able to locate 1311 of these documents in the Scopus database. The three research

¹ Quote attributed to Price, ‘Of sealing wax and string’ [Natural History. 84(1) 49056. 1984] in Garfield’s obituary of Price (published in Current Contents, #28, p. 3-7, July 9, 1984.)

² “I do not publish with the principal objective of debate for an amiable public, but in the hope of adding something to knowledge before the audience of peers.” Price (1970), ‘Smiles at the Unobtrusive’. Nature 226: 985.

communities from our model with the largest number of Xu's articles are described in the following section. The 10-year history of their production, import and export activity (2011-2020) is then used to predict their activities for the next 4 years.

Section 3: Data

The 1311 Scopus papers in Xu's corpus are spread among 759 research communities, of which 31 contain at least 5 papers as shown in Figure 1. The top three communities comprise the bibliometric core for this research area. Most of the other communities are application areas where the articles characterize specific emerging topics after they have emerged.

Figure 1. Communities with at least 5 papers from the Xu corpus on emerging topics. Bar height reflect numbers of papers. Labels include number, key phrase and annual growth rate of communities as of 2010. Color reflects the dominant field associated with the community (see legend).

Community #5528

The largest number of documents from Xu's corpus ($n=122$) are assigned to this research community. This is the 'science mapping' community that is presented in the introduction of this article. Most of our (Boyack & Klavans) publications are assigned to this community. One of the early efforts of Eugene Garfield (the founder of ISI) was to test whether citation data could replicate Isaac Asimov's history of the development of DNA (Garfield, Sher, & Torpie, 1964). The first maps of science at ISI were also part of this effort (Small, 1977). Some of the current highly cited documents in this community introduce software that allows

users to create their own maps for descriptive purposes (van Eck & Waltman, 2010) or predictive purposes (Chen, 2006). There were 2633 papers published in this community between 2000-2020.

The trends in production, import and export are presented in Figure 2. In order to interpret this graph, it's important to understand that, **under *ceteris paribus* conditions, the graph should appear as having three flat lines, with the production, import and export lines super-imposed.** Any pattern that is different from this pattern is providing fundamental insights about the unique characteristics of a research community.

Figure 2. Community #5528 – Trends in production, import and export activity

The reason we should expect three flat super-imposed lines is based on the following. The y axis in Figure 2 represents the yearly share of activities. 10^{-4} means that 1/10,000 of the activity in a year is associated with the research community.³ Shares are used (where the sum is 1.0 over all communities) because, if we have *ceteris paribus* conditions (i.e., everything grows and interacts at the same rate), the share of activity should be constant regardless of what the activity is. The fact that some communities have higher imports than exports (or production vs. imports, or production vs. exports) tells us something unique about that community. Use of log plots allows constant growth to be seen as a straight (rather than curved) line. This allows us to detect discontinuity in growth rates.

Figure 2 shows that the three lines are relatively flat and similar from 2010-2015, while they were sloped from 2000-2010. But export behavior has recently increased dramatically (over 11%/year) for the 2015-2020 time period. Ten-year average growth rates for each curve are used as the basis for the 2020-2024 forecast in Figure 1 and subsequent figures.

Community #1644

The second largest number of documents from Xu's corpus (n=32) are assigned to this research community, which focuses on patent analysis. The roots of this community go back to studies by economists on the role of patents as an economic indicator (Griliches, 1998) and as one of the mechanisms for appropriating the benefits of innovation (Levin, Klevorick,

³ Since, in 2020, the number of papers in the entire Scopus database was roughly 3 million, this research community was producing about 300 papers in 2020.

Nelson, & Winter, 1987). Patent citation databases play an import role in this community in much the same way literature citation databases are important to #5528. Corporate actors have a much larger voice in this research community than in #5528 (3.4% vs. 1.8% of recent articles are by authors associated with a corporation). Government actors also have a slightly larger voice (5.7% vs. 4.0% of recent publications). There were 4237 papers published in this community between 2000-2020.

The trends in production, import and export are presented in Figure 3. This is a pattern that most closely represents the ceteris paribus conditions- three relatively flat lines. Exports (which are usually aligned with applications) exceed imports (which are usually aligned with new ways to address the central problems of patent analysis) – a pattern that would be consistent with a research community that is more oriented to commercial and government applications.

Figure 3. Community #1644 – Trends in production, import and export activity

Community #423

The third largest number of documents from Xu's corpus (n=16) are assigned to this research community. This community focuses on the creation of bibliometric indicators (such as the journal impact factor and H-index) that are now commonly used to evaluate research activities around the world. There is a very large import-export relationship between this community and #5528. The knowledge about how to analyze large literature databases is applicable to both research communities.

The trends in import, production and export are presented in Figure 4. These are the least normal patterns among the three communities in that the lines are neither flat nor close to each other. Growth rates in production and import activity went from positive to negative. Relatively fewer papers are being produced by this community. One interpretation of fewer imports is that members of this community are relying less and less on the knowledge that is generated in other research communities.

Figure 4. Community #423 – Trends in production, import and export activity

Section 4: Discussion and Implications

Overall, the data suggest that the area of emerging research topics is rooted in communities that focus on the analysis of literature databases (#5528 and #423) and patent databases (#1644). #5528 is the dominant community that analyzes literature databases for the purpose of analyzing structure including detection of emerging research. #423 and #1644 likely appear on the list in that literature-based indicators and patent-based indicators are at times linked to emerging topics. This interpretation simplifies the analysis. Research on emerging topics has a core community that is methodologically driven. Two closely related communities deal with indicators associated with literature and patents. Methods from these communities are then applied widely to case studies in many other areas of the literature. Furthermore, comparison of Figures 2-4 suggests that growth is most likely to occur in #5528, especially in terms of exports where products (tools to identify structure and emergence) are increasingly used by other communities. In contrast, production and imports are likely to decline in both of the other clusters.

Details about the import and export interactions between communities provide additional information to help us understand their networks. For instance, Figure 5 shows the 20 largest trading partners for #5528. The top five include the two communities already identified (#423 & #1644), a very large theory-driven community that looks at scale-free networks (#67) and communities that use the scientific literature to look at scientific collaboration (#5685) and interdisciplinarity (#5662). Of these, #5528 has been a net importer from #423 in most years (colored red), while imports and exports with #1644 and #5685 have been relatively balanced. The bottom of the figure shows that most of the other top 20 interactions are net export, where #5528 is exporting tools and methods to other communities.

We note that this is only the tip of the iceberg. #5528 has imports and/or exports with 1333 other communities, of which Figure 5 shows only 20. While the other interactions are smaller, in the aggregate they give rise to the full import and export profiles shown in Figure 2 which shows the strong growth in exports in the most recent five years.

The patent analysis community (#1644) has imports and/or exports with 1168 other communities. The eight largest trading partners for #1644 (see Figure 6) are completely different than those of #5528. These are with #236 (dynamic capabilities of a firm), #639

(academic entrepreneurship), #172 (regional innovation systems), #466 (human capital and economic growth) and #7241 (cooperation/competition). #5528 is only the ninth largest trading partner for #1644, and thus is not among its most important. #1644 is clearly embedded in a network aimed at economic application rather than academic characterization, despite the fact that #1644 and #5528 both have some association with emerging topics.

Figure 5. Community #5528 – Details on import and export activity with other communities. Red bars show net imports while green bars show net exports.

Figure 6. Community #1644 – Details on import and export activity with other communities. Red bars show net imports while green bars show net exports.

Section 5: Specific and Broader Applications

We have presented a novel method for tracking the production, import and export activities of tens of thousands of research communities with the intent to identify which of these will have exceptional growth in the future. The proposed method also provides a common framework

for understanding how a research area is evolving. By decomposing a field into its component communities, and understanding the unique network associated with each part, one can get a much more nuanced view about the past, present and hopefully future direction for any area of research.

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